

Questionnaire for the Evaluation of the AgenticAIFlow DSL
Using the Perception Variables: Ease of Use (PEOU),
Usefulness (PU), and Intention to Use (ITU)

No.	Question
PEOU1	The AgenticAIFlow DSL user interface is intuitive and easy to understand?
PEOU2	The graphical notation used by the AgenticAIFlow DSL to represent its components is intuitive and easy to understand?
PEOU3	The methodological process for designing and implementing agentic AI workflows is easy to understand and apply?
PEOU4	The AgenticAIFlow DSL facilitates the design and execution of agentic AI workflows?
PU1	The AgenticAIFlow DSL reduces the time required to automate agentic AI workflows aimed at solving complex problems?
PU2	The AgenticAIFlow DSL is useful for automating agentic AI workflows that solve complex problems?
PU3	The AgenticAIFlow DSL improves your performance in designing and implementing agentic AI workflows?
PU4	The documents generated by the automated workflows meet the predefined quality requirements?
PU5	The documents generated by the automated workflows contribute to achieving the intended objectives?
ITU1	Would you use the AgenticAIFlow DSL in future projects?
ITU2	Would you recommend using the AgenticAIFlow DSL to other professionals and researchers?
OQ1	Do you have any suggestions for improving the proposed solution? (open-ended question)